

Chemical speciation of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} binary complexes of L-phenylalanine in CTAB-water mixtures

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of L-phenylalanine in 0.0–2.5% w/v cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)-water mixtures maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 M at 303 K has been studied pH metrically. The active forms of ligand are LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻. The predominant species detected are ML₂, ML₂H and ML₃. Models containing different numbers of species were refined by using the computer program MINIQUAD 75. The best-fit chemical models were arrived at based on statistical parameters. The trend in variation of complex stability constants with change in the mole fraction of the medium is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : Chemical speciation, L-phenylalanine, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, metals, stability constants.

Introduction

Investigations of acido-basic equilibria of amino acids, their interaction with metal ions in media of varying ionic strength, temperature and dielectric constant throw light on the mechanism of enzyme-catalyzed reactions. Although it is known that the polarity of the active site cavities in proteins is lower than that of the bulk, a direct measurement of the dielectric constant is not possible. Comparing the formation constants of acido-basic equilibria and/or metal complex equilibria with those at biological centers offers a way to estimate the effective dielectric constant or equivalent solution dielectric constant for the active site cavity¹. This brought a renaissance in the study of complex equilibria in aqua-organic and aquamicellar mixtures apart from its established utility in understanding solute-solvent interactions, increasing sensitivity of reactions of analytical and industrial importance and solubilising ligands or their metal complexes.

Chemical speciation of metals is important for an understanding of their distribution, mobility, bioavailability, toxicity and for setting environmental quality standards.

Bioavailability of a particular metal depends on its complex chemical reactions of dissolution, binding and complexation with the constituents of the environmental aquatic phase². The activity of bacteria increase the concentration of dissolved organic carbon and decreases the pH value of water. This causes an increase in the complexation and mobility of a metal³. Complexation significantly decreases bioavailability.

Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium and mercury are toxic substances which exert adverse effects on neurological, reproductive, renal and hematological systems in humans and animals. Organo-mercury and lead compounds exhibit toxic effect on the central nervous system⁴. Similarly cadmium exhibits various chronic and acute disorders like testicular atrophy, hypertension, damage to kidneys and bones, anemia and Itai-Itai^{5–9}. Hence, the stability constants of the binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} have been determined using pH metry. These values are potentially useful to environmental and biological problems^{10–12}.

Micelles alter the reaction rates and shift equilibria primarily by concentrating reactants within the small vol-

ume of micellar pseudo phase. The extent of change is a product of the micellar effect on the reaction within the micellar pseudo phase and the distribution of reactants between the two phases. The effect of micelles on overall reaction rates and equilibria depends upon the incorporation of solutes into the micellar pseudo phase. CTAB is a cationic surfactant which tends to denature proteins and profoundly influences the bulk properties of physiological systems. It can solubilise, concentrate and compartmentalize ions and molecules¹³. Hence, the influence of cationic micellar media (CTAB) on the chemical speciation of L-phenylalanine has been investigated.

Experimental

Materials :

L-Phenylalanine (E. Merck, Germany) solution (0.05 mol L⁻¹) was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. CTAB (Merck, India) was used as received. 2 mol L⁻¹ sodium nitrate (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.1 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solutions of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and 0.05 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solution of Hg^{II} nitrates were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple-distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹⁴. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{15,16}.

Apparatus :

The titrimetric data were obtained using ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01), which was calibrated with 0.05 mol L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen phthalate in acidic region and 0.01 mol L⁻¹ borax solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred CTAB-water mixture containing the inert electrolyte. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of CTAB-water mixtures (0.0–2.5% w/v) by maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium nitrate at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. The effect of variation in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error, and dissolved

carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode was accounted for in the form of correction factor^{17,18}.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with CTAB-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 mL. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0 in the case of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} and 1 : 7.5, 1 : 8.5 and 1 : 10.0 in the case of Hg^{II}) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹⁹.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²⁰ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using the pH-metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75²¹, which exploit the advantage of the constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constants of L-phenylalanine were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the mole fraction of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the final best-fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. Very low-standard deviation in overall stability constants (log β) signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis²².

Residual analysis :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the re-

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}-phenylalanine complexes in CTAB-water mixtures

% w/v CTAB	log β _{mlh} (SD)			pH-range	NP	U _{corr}	χ ²	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	ML ₂	ML ₂ H	ML ₃							
Pb ^{II}										
0.0	6.38(15)	15.03(14)	9.25(18)	7.0–9.2	22	19.44	21.52	–0.01	4.92	0.0162
0.5	6.71(24)	15.25(21)	9.65(26)	7.0–9.2	21	21.11	4.17	0.26	2.77	0.0528
1.0	7.32(22)	15.02(22)	10.14(21)	7.0–8.5	18	12.66	5.26	–0.33	2.14	0.0405
1.5	6.48(21)	14.24(22)	10.10(20)	7.0–8.7	23	24.50	2.30	0.14	2.67	0.0531
2.0	6.91(19)	15.18(23)	10.17(22)	7.4–9.2	23	7.00	15.06	1.27	6.69	0.0598
2.5	6.93(21)	15.21(23)	10.21(25)	7.6–8.5	19	33.12	2.09	–0.01	3.69	0.0599
Cd ^{II}										
0.0	6.27(21)	14.65(22)	9.06(19)	7.0–9.2	21	13.33	5.95	–0.53	3.00	0.0358
0.5	6.59(15)	14.96(20)	9.70(21)	7.2–8.7	17	1.43	7.82	0.29	3.09	0.0133
1.0	6.77(19)	14.35(22)	9.82(23)	7.3–8.7	19	5.62	4.05	1.46	6.38	0.0279
1.5	6.25(23)	14.36(29)	9.48(24)	7.0–9.2	24	5.71	36.00	3.19	16.66	0.0278
2.0	6.59(23)	14.78(21)	9.66(22)	7.6–9.2	26	76.95	3.23	0.89	5.25	0.0961
2.5	6.62(22)	14.46(21)	9.72(23)	7.6–8.5	19	22.50	1.53	0.92	4.36	0.0501
Hg ^{II}										
0.0	6.88(14)	15.34(24)	9.42(27)	6.0–9.6	24	5.71	11.33	0.21	4.43	0.0246
0.5	6.29(22)	15.06(17)	9.36(22)	6.0–8.5	14	1.82	3.33	0.40	5.12	0.0137
1.0	6.63(21)	14.57(22)	10.03(23)	7.4–8.7	22	25.26	5.27	1.36	5.74	0.0601
1.5	6.70(21)	14.53(22)	9.90(21)	6.0–8.5	20	0.59	4.00	0.25	3.10	0.0275
2.0	6.59(22)	14.46(21)	9.67(23)	7.3–8.4	17	19.28	2.49	0.27	2.94	0.0442
2.5	7.00(22)	14.33(24)	9.71(25)	7.0–8.4	22	32.11	6.97	0.27	2.87	0.0603

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP - m)$; m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points; SD = standard deviation.

siduals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian or normal distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should ideally be equal to zero. If statistical measures of the residuals and the errors assumed in the models are not significantly different from each other, the model is said to be adequate. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis that the errors are random, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , Skewness, Kurtosis and R-factor. These statistical parameters show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in CTAB-water mixtures, as discussed below.

In the present study, the χ^2 values are less than the table values, and so the models are accepted. The Kurtosis values in this study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern. The values of Skewness recorded in Table 1 are between –0.33 and 1.27 for Pb^{II}, –0.53 and 1.46 for Cd^{II} and 0.21 and 1.36 for Hg^{II}. These data

evidence that the residuals form part of a normal distribution. Hence, least square method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from crystallographic R-values. These statistical parameters thus show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in CTAB media.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to rely upon the best-fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was undertaken by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand, metal, log *F* and volume (Table 2). The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > metal > ligand > volume > log *F*. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Cd^{II}-phenylalanine complex stability constants in 0.5% w/v CTAB-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β _{mlh} (SD)		
		120	121	130
Acid	0	6.59(15)	14.96(20)	9.70(21)
	-5	7.25(33)	Rejected	10.98(14)
	-2	7.14(22)	15.56(34)	10.74(31)
	+2	6.10(14)	14.38(19)	8.64(31)
	+5	5.29(9)	13.37(37)	Rejected
Alkali	-5	5.00(12)	13.40(32)	Rejected
	-2	6.07(13)	14.34(19)	8.44(38)
	+2	7.09(28)	15.59(41)	10.84(38)
	+5	6.83(40)	Rejected	11.14(15)
Ligand	-5	6.56(21)	15.06(20)	9.99(19)
	-2	6.58(17)	15.00(20)	9.82(20)
	+2	6.59(14)	14.91(21)	9.58(22)
	+5	6.58(12)	14.85(21)	9.39(25)
Metal	-5	6.58(19)	15.01(23)	9.83(23)
	-2	6.59(16)	14.98(21)	9.75(22)
	+2	6.58(14)	14.94(19)	9.65(21)
	+5	6.58(12)	14.91(18)	9.58(20)
Volume	-5	6.49(19)	14.97(20)	9.72(21)
	-2	6.51(19)	14.98(20)	9.74(21)
	+2	6.54(19)	15.01(20)	9.79(21)
	+5	6.56(19)	15.03(20)	9.81(21)
	log F	-5	6.52(19)	14.99(20)
-2		6.53(19)	15.00(20)	9.76(21)
+2		6.59(15)	14.96(20)	9.71(21)
+5		6.59(15)	14.96(20)	9.72(21)

confirm the suitability of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best-fit models.

Effect of solvent :

Many workers were opinion that both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acido-basic equilibria; one dominates the other, depending upon the nature of solute and solvent²³⁻²⁵. Born's classical treatment²⁶ holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. The effect of surfactant on complex equilibria and apparent shift in the magnitude of stability constants in micellar media can be attributed²⁷ to the creation of a concentration gradient of proton between the interface and the bulk solution. The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant, and oppositely charged ions

are concentrated in the Stern layer²⁸.

CTAB has a positive polar head and hence, negatively charged ligand ions are concentrated in the Stern layer where as hydrogen ions are pushed into the bulk solvent. The deprotonated carboxyl ions are stabilized compared to the protonated forms by the cationic micelles due to the formation of ion pairs. The stability constants (log β) varied linearly with mole fraction of CTAB due to the polarity of the medium, charge on the micellar surface and due to the electrostatic forces/hydrophobic interactions operating between the complex species and micellar surface. The species are stabilized in the micellar medium with opposite charges due to electrostatic interactions. The linear or almost linear variations of stability constants (log β) with the mole fraction of CTAB (Fig. 1) indicate the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces^{29,30}. The non-linearity may be due to the relative contributions of the structure-forming nature and complexing ability of CTAB. One of the reasons for such behavior is accumulation of metal ion and ligand on the surface of the micelles with increased concentration of surfactant.

Distribution diagrams :

L-Phenylalanine is a bidentate ligand that has one dissociable (carboxyl group) and one associable (amino) protons. The different forms of phenylalanine are LH₂⁺, LH, and L⁻ in the pH range 1.6–6.0, 2.0–10.0, > 7.0, respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML₂, ML₂H, ML₃ for Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}. The formation of various phenylalanine complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

The species $ML_2H_2^{2+}$, $ML_3H_3^{2+}$, $ML_3H_2^+$ could not be detected in the present study probably because they are formed at very low pH. Some typical distribution diagrams in CTAB-water mixtures are shown in Fig. 2. They indicate that the binary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} are formed in the pH range 5.0–10.0. The species ML_2H , ML_2 , ML_3 are formed in the pH range of 6.0–9.6. ML_2H is formed at lower pH with higher percentage [Equilibria (6), (7), (8) and (18)]. ML_2 , ML_3 are simultaneously formed with the increasing pH. ML_2 , ML_3 species percentage successively increases with increasing pH. Successive deprotonation of ML_2H forms ML_2 beyond a pH 9.0. The percentage of the ML_3 species increases successively with increasing in pH up to 9.0. The concentration of ML_2H species decreased, while the concentration of ML_2 and ML_3 increased in the pH range 7.0–9.0 [Equilibria (9), (10) and (11)]. ML_3 formed at higher pH with high percentage [Equilibria (11), (17), (22) and (25)].

Fig. 1. Variation of overall stability constant values of metal-L-phenylalanine complexes with mole fraction ($n_x \times 10^3$) of CTAB-water mixtures : (a) Pb^{II}, (b) Cd^{II}, (c) Hg^{II}, (■)log β_{ML₂}, (▲) log β_{ML₃}, (●) log β_{ML₂H}.

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of L-phenylalanine in 2.5% w/v CTAB-water mixture : (a) Pb^{II} , (b) Cd^{II} and (c) Hg^{II} .

Structures of complexes :

When the second donor site of L-phenylalanine is a nitrogen atom, marked bidentate behavior is frequently found, more so when the additional chelation results in a five membered ring (Fig. 3). Octahedral structures are proposed to the complexes of all the metal ions. The VSEPR theory suggests that Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes shall be octahedral because there are six outer electron pairs.

Amino nitrogen atoms can associate with hydrogen ions in physiological pH ranges. Hence, there is often significant competition between hydrogen and metal ion for this second donor site. This situation results in the simultaneous existence of a number of equilibria producing an array of successively protonated complexes. Hence, protonated complex species are detected in the present study. Amino nitrogen and carboxyl oxygen of L-phenylalanine participate in bonding with metal ions. This argument supports the structures of complexes proposed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Structure of L-phenylalanine complexes where S is either solvent or water molecules.

Conclusions

- (i) The present biomimetic studies of metal ion complexes with L-phenylalanine in CTAB-water mixtures indicate that all the complexes were protonated in acidic pH values.
- (ii) The predominant species detected were ML₂, ML₂H and ML₃.
- (iii) The log β values linearly variation with mole fraction values of the medium, indicating the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) The order of the compounds influencing the magnitudes of the stability constants due to the incorporation of errors was alkali > acid > ligand > metal > total volume > log F.
- (v) The higher concentration of free metal in low pH values make the metal more bioavailable, more so in the case of toxic metals. At higher pH values, the higher concentrations of complex chemical species indicate that the metals are more amenable for transportation at higher pH values.

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